

Logical Map: Data and Material Flow Visualization

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Abstract. Mind mapping is a visual tool used to associate ideas and organize information around a topic of interest in a flexible way, without the need for complex software or services. All can participate without technical knowledge or background. Mind mapping techniques are not easily delegated or reusable, because the entities and topic of interest are unique to the particular map. It is difficult to deal with shifts in perspective or focus, as they are usually just one level. Knowledge graphs are similar to mind mapping, but benefit from shared meaning through specified syntax and definition of entities and relations. However, they are often too cumbersome to use freestyle, like mind mapping, so computers are used to create and visualize the graph. This often requires experts, complex software, and external services. I describe a method that combines the benefits of both mind mapping and knowledge graphs, while addressing their limitations. It provides combined data and material flow visualization with nested organization, simple syntax, merge capabilities, real-time human cognition support, and perspective shift adaptability. With just one day of training, participants can collaborate on new maps using this method.

1. Introduction

The motivation for this work comes from my experience analyzing data flow for a non-technical public finance group at a global law firm. They were using physical paper to author the bonds, and it needed to be converted to electronic. Most in the group were resistant to change, and suspicious of workflow applications. Rather than gather requirements and design the new system for them, I used a simple data flow model, and collaboratively designed the new system with them. All in the group were able to understand a simplified version of Gane and Sarson's method of structured analysis [1]. Even the most resistant, non-technical person in the group was able to point at a process and explain a flaw they saw in the represented flow. This demonstrated that systems could be improved and visualized by those whose hands and minds directly used the system, and were committed to its smooth operation, even though they had no technical experience. I used this method several times with subsequent efforts, and saw similar levels of engagement by stakeholders. Unfortunately, the need for this kind of collaborative analysis and visualization was abandoned by most organizations, who tend to purchase services rather than handle the system design internally.

Outside of my professional life in IT and system analysis, in 2002 I learned about e-waste from rapid information technology growth [2]. I joined an energy transitions group in 2010, and learned more about our situation with minerals, fossil fuels, and energy [3]. This led to my understanding of the unfolding metacrisis [4]. Wilderness training often uses S.T.O.P.: Stop, Think, Observe, Plan before action [5]. I realized that, while not valued at current system complexity, my simple analysis technique might be useful during each crisis where it was prudent to stop, think observe, and plan.

Figure 1: Symbols

Figure 2: Mom Delivery

Rather than view collapse as a single event with no recovery, I see many events and an opportunity during each crisis, part of a long string of collapse and recovery cycles with a general trend of simplification [6]. Those same organizations that moved their reporting, analysis and intelligence systems to cloud, and relied on external services for system knowledge, would quickly become desperate as broader systems collapsed. The tools documented in this paper can work as a cognitive aid without computers [7], and help evaluate situations in an objective way, so failing systems can be refactored with long term objectives that align with a more developed understanding of progress [8]. While it is possible to

use these ideas without computers, they are quite useful for organization and visualization. I've created small, simple tools that help. The Logical Map application is less than 1MB, with all needed libraries, and will run on any OS without external services. It does not require an internet connection. It uses existing standards, and is free and open-source software.

2. Combined Data and Material Flows

Not everything important consists of data and material flows. Human touch, both protection from negative and positive, are important for our well-being. These would be good use cases for mind mapping [9]. Most critical items are material, along with data about how to obtain. Food, water, shelter and first aid primarily involve data and material flows.

Consider water. There are pipes, water towers, pumps, dams, faucets and reservoirs related to obtaining potable water for most people. It isn't as simple as a town well [10]. Sure, right now it is common to pay the water bill with a phone app, and the water just appears at the tap; however, if the town has a water outage because a dam or aqueduct fails, visualizing the material aspects of the system will quickly become a priority, as well as the knowledge of the related systems and the data flows that operate it [11]. Combining these two on one map aids in system cognition, as there is no need to switch perspectives for the view.

Fig. 1 shows the three classes of entities in the model. The teal rectangles are agents that are a source or destination of data for processes. An agent moving a cup from a conveyor belt to a box uses data to transform the cups location. An agent can be a person, an AI, group of people, or sensor. The light blue, rounded rectangles change data or materials through processes or transforms. A process might be a report or calculation. A transform changes materials from one form to another. The dashed line means data is flowing. A solid line means materials are flowing. The orange-brown rectangle stores things at rest. Datastores store data at rest; it might be a stack of paper in a folder or a disk drive. Locations store materials at rest. Between entities, lines show the direction of flow. The type of flow is determined by either the process or transform connection. For instance, an agent provides operational data and receives operational feedback from a transform. That same agent can use data from an external process which can interact with other agents, other processes, or datastores. Hovering the mouse pointer over the line in a web browser shows details about what is flowing. Only processes and transforms can connect to stores at rest. Agents cannot connect to agents. Fig. 3 shows a driver as an agent steering a car. The driver relies on knowledge about how to drive. This process is fed by what the driver sees through their eyes, which relies on data from the retina.

Figure 3: Drive

3. Syntax and Merge

The syntax used to create maps is called Graph Stack format. It is simple text. **::** signifies a command. The **:: level** command requires one or more lines immediately after to designate the level. The first line is always Top, since all maps have a top level. The Logical Map application on the website only views one level at a time on the left, and doesn't show the extra level information, but it can be seen on the rendered map, and when using the export feature [12]. Sublevels are entered line-by-line until the next command.

Graph theory is not required to understand Logical Map; however, I often intermix graph terms, and the concepts of Logical Map are based in graph theory, so it is easier to describe what is happening with Graph Stack format. The full set of graph translations is in the software repository for Logical Map [13].

Fig. 2. is a graph. Nodes can have graphs located entirely inside them, indicated by the magenta dot in the upper-left corner. I'm calling these graphs sublevels. Only processes or transforms can contain other sublevels. If we call Fig. 2 the Top level, Fig. 3 is a sublevel with the designation Top.Drive, entirely contained in the Drive node in Fig. 2. **:: locations** and **:: transforms** are nodes. **:: items** and **:: note** are attributes. **:: both**, **:: back**, and **:: forward** are edges that indicate direction of flow. Attributes are indicated by an orange dot in the upper-right corner.

```
:: back  
Store  
:: items  
Food  
:: forward  
Home  
:: items  
Food  
:: agents  
Mom
```

Figure 5: Food

transforms, is a node, so the current node state is reset to Drive. The command **:: note** applies to the last node, edge, or level. In Fig 4. the note applies to the transform Drive. If the note appeared right below Top, it would apply to the graph Top. Edges apply to the last node. Store in Fig. 5 applies to Drive. The command **:: items** apply to the edge, so Food flows. Fig 6 resets the level to Top.Drive. Any commands after this would be entered on the subgraph Top.Drive, one level down from Top.

Different people and groups can work with Graph Stack text independently and combine them later. Duplicates are removed automatically; however, only text with no outstanding operations can be used. The best way to do this is to only concatenate text that starts with **:: level** and redefine the nodes, as all of the nodes and edges are reset. Alternatively, it is possible to add the entity that is being referenced. Fig. 5 starts out by defining the edge Drive to Store, so in order to merge, the lines **:: transforms** and Drive would need to be added to the top of the file to successfully merge with Fig. 6. Likewise, the lines **:: agents** and Mom need to be added to the top of Fig. 6 to merge with Fig. 5 and Fig. 4 to create the graph in Fig 2. The lines are case sensitive, so they can also function as labels.

```
:: level  
Top  
:: locations  
Home  
Store  
:: transforms  
Drive  
:: note  
Gas gauge broken
```

Figure 4: Mom

Figs. 4,5 and 6, when put together in order, form the graph in Fig. 2. We can describe it in English using our new graph vocabulary. Graph Top has three nodes: Home, Store, and Drive. Drive is a transform that has a note attribute "Gas gauge broken". Fig. 5 is a continuation, so Food flows over an edge from Store to Home via Drive. Mom is an agent node. Fig. 6 forms the rest of the graph in Fig. 2. Mom provides and receives operational data to/from the Drive transform node, which is a sublevel as well.

Graph Stack works based on stack order. Commands apply to the last graph, node and edge. The lines following a command have different meaning, depending on the state of the stack. For instance, if **:: level** is entered, it resets the state of nodes and edges. Until a node is defined, any attributes refer to the **:: level** not the node. Fig 4. lines Home and Store refer to the last command, so they are locations. The following command, **::**

```
:: both  
Drive  
:: items  
Operational Data  
:: level  
Top  
Drive
```

Figure 6: Operation

4. Nested Organization

Nesting is when a process or transform entities contains other sublevels. The Drive transform in Fig. 2 encloses all of Fig. 3. Fig. 3 could have further sublevels, much like a Russian nesting doll.

Figure 7: Top

The benefits of nesting are clearer in Fig 7., the top level. This represents the major concerns of a town without the diagram being overwhelming. The numbers at the top of processes and transforms indicate the level. The KorTalos process in Fig 7. has a designation of 0.1, which means it is the first process or transform on the Top level 0. The numbers are unique so they can be referenced in other documentation. The Logical Map application increments these automatically and will shift numbers if transform or process nodes are added for initial layout. These can be easily pinned by adding an attribute command of `:: num` to the application. Fig 9. shows a level that is two levels down from Fig 7. The text version of the nesting is indicated on the left with \rightarrow to indicate the depth at that line.

If the map becomes too cluttered, a new target can easily be created with a new level. To simplify Fig. 9, processes 0.1.3.12.1, 0.1.3.12.1.2, and 0.1.3.12.1.4 and associated entities could be moved into a new process called Advertising and Engagement, which is shown in Fig. 10. Government Leaders, Fodder and Mudder, and IdentiTroll connect to this new process, leaving just six entities on the new Social Fanisizer level in Fig. 8. No-

Top
 \rightarrow KorTalos
 $\rightarrow \rightarrow$ CustomerRelationshipManager
 $\rightarrow \rightarrow \rightarrow$ SocialFanisizer

Figure 8: Modified Social Fanisizer

How this simplification reveals something about the system that wasn't as apparent before. Social Fanisizer uses Troll Farms for Advertising and Engagement; however, this is not what the Advertising and Engagement level perceives. They think of it as VerifyID.

When refactoring levels, the Logical Map application has an export feature so that multiple entries can be done more efficiently and without risking the overall model. For smaller changes, delete the entity by putting // in front of it and save the changes with a backtick (`). To create the new Advertising and Engagement level, add a new `:: level` with four lines after: Top, KorTalos, Customer Relationship Manager, Social Fanisizer, and Advertising and Engagement. Then, adjust the new entity on the level. See References for before and after Graph Stack text [14] [15].

Figure 9: Social Fanisizer

5. Real-time Human Cognition

When collaborating on a system map in a group to solve a common problem, it is important to keep the number of tools you use and the relationships simple. Consider a checklist. Anybody can create a checklist easily and start using it and experience the benefit quickly [16]. It is a simple cognitive engagement that starts small and expands as needed, when there is time for more nuance. Roughly three tools and two teams can be juggled for shared cultural cognition [17]. While the exercise of mapping out material and data flow is not the same thing, it does indicate a target of what to expect when creating maps in real-time. The limited entity classes and relations are roughly in line with the limits of shared cultural cognition.

More sophisticated tools require experts or computers to manage the complexity of the visualizations. This forms a catch-22. When broader systems fail, more sophisticated tools might not be available. How do you map in real-time? It has to be simple. Logical map automatically routes the connections on the map in real-time. In a collaborative environment a correction to the map is instant, so others can see what is being discussed and visualize the relations, so they can contribute

to further changes. Each map level has all the detail needed to function on its own. The full map, title, and even notes about the level are included, so they can be distributed individually.

6. Perspective Shift

We all experience the world in different ways, from different perspectives. In Fig. 2, the perspective is broader; Mom is bringing home milk from the store. When we zoom in, we are concerned with the details of driving. We could zoom in further into Steer in Fig. 3 and the perspective shift could include other perspectives, like mechanical and tactile feedback through the steering wheel. The model I describe only enforces the relations within the class of data or material transform/process entities. I do not enforce any meaning on the storage or agents between levels. Mom is the bringer of things to the home in Fig 2. In Fig 3. the agent is simply Driver, which could be anybody, as our perspective is now about driving. It is entirely within the Drive transform.

Figure 10: Advertising and Engagement

What we name things changes as well. At a top level, for instance, everybody in an organization should know where their revenue comes from. It might be as simple as a flow of revenue from subscribing customers to the business's bank. This is all that most need to know at the top level. The view from the perspective of a computer technician maintaining physical connectivity to the Internet for the business to process incoming revenue is going to be quite different than the accounts receivable group in accounting. At the top level, where the money is tracked and stored is not important to understanding the perspective. The company stores it; it could be a bank or a safe. A computer technician might include routers, switches, and Internet service providers in their day-to-day map of important aspects related to obtaining revenue. An accountant doing billing would have a different idea of the aspects, and call them different things, but it still falls under obtaining revenue. The logical idea of that transform still holds, much like a road map. A road on a high-level map might show a 1 inch segment between cities 200 miles apart. There are many different but useful perspectives within that that would clutter up the map if included. Some are data, and some are material perspectives. Regardless, it is generally possible to take a transform of obtaining revenue and break it out into sublevels at material and data transform nodes yet still retain the power

of different perspectives. This differs from formal knowledge graphs, as only **:: locations** and **:: transforms** provide nesting. This is a feature, not a liability, because of perspective shift. This also facilitates delegation, as an extensive set of common terms doesn't need to be established and taught. All the team needs to know is where they fall under **:: locations** and **:: transforms** hierarchies.

7. Conclusion

I have described a way of thinking about systems and a specific technical implementation of these ideas that facilitate quick visualization with minimal reliance on external parties. This is done with a lightweight model that combines material and data flow in a way that is easy to understand in real-time without reliance on consultants or external technology. The model can be easily delegated, as meaning is not retained between levels, and this also helps resolve differences in points of view. I use a simple text format to minimize effort and technical knowledge needed to create the maps, and specify the requirements for merging the work of different groups. These methods and tools can help us refactor our systems as broader systems we rely on are failing.

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